

SERVICE QUALITY AND CUSTOMER SATISFACTION OF AIR EXPRESS CARGO OPERATORS: BASIS FOR LOGISTICS ACTIVITY MODEL

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the service quality and customer satisfaction of Air Express Cargo Operators (AECO) in Western Visayas, particularly in Iloilo, and assessed the significance and extent of their relationship. Using a descriptive-correlational design, data were collected from 91 respondents during the third quarter of 2024. The findings revealed that respondents rated AECO's service quality as "very important" based on the SERVQUAL dimensions. Customer satisfaction, measured in terms of expectations, was rated as "Satisfied," while satisfaction based on customer perceptions was rated as "very satisfied". Notably, the study found a positive, very high, and statistically significant relationship between the empathy dimension of AECO's services and customer satisfaction with reliability in terms of expectations. A similarly strong correlation was found between AECO's assurance dimension and customer satisfaction with assurance in terms of perceptions. Additionally, a high and significant association was observed between AECO's tangibility dimension and customer satisfaction with empathy in terms of perceptions. This finding suggests the need for technological upgrades and the proposed model for AECO to improve service efficiency and customer satisfaction.

Keywords: *Air Express Cargo Operators, Service Quality, Logistics Activity Model, Customer Satisfaction*

INTRODUCTION

In the Philippines, the courier and logistics industry has undergone significant growth in recent years, driven by the increase in online shopping and the rising demand for reliable and efficient delivery services. Air express has established itself as a prominent provider of domestic air freight and express courier services, consolidating its position as a major player in this fiercely competitive industry.

According to International Trade Organization (2022) the e-commerce industry in the Philippines recorded a total sales revenue of \$17 billion in 2021. Projections indicate that this figure would see a growth rate of 17% and reach \$24 billion by the year 2025. Moreover, these ecommerce platforms facilitate the sale of goods originating from Asia-Pacific markets that have established free trade agreements with the Philippines. The most sought-after product categories on these platforms include electronics, fashion, furniture, health, and household care. On the other hand, Periyasamy et al. (2023) have found that ecommerce platforms frequently encounter problems with delivery. These problems include delays, failures, and missed deliveries, as well as damaged or lost orders. In addition, inefficient customer support and inconsistent delivery experiences contribute to these challenges. Furthermore, international shipping can worsen these issues, creating difficulties in managing logistics activities. Therefore, AECOs play a vital function in the transportation of goods, especially those that necessitate prompt attention and handle time-sensitive shipments. Furthermore, courier delivery services play a crucial role in supporting ecommerce by ensuring that client expectations are met and orders are effectively fulfilled.

In order to tackle the difficulties faced by the participants, this study will utilize the SERVQUAL model. The SERVQUAL approach evaluates service quality using five dimensions: tangibility, assurance, reliability, responsiveness, and empathy. By implementing this methodology, the study will offer useful insights into areas where enhancements can be implemented to augment the overall quality of service and foster trust, as proposed by Tang et al. (2022). Furthermore, comprehending the level of service excellence will facilitate the creation of a focused plan that meets the expectations of stakeholders and establishes a framework for the logistics activity model.

Logistics encompasses the efficient coordination and oversight of all activities related to the transportation and storage of goods and services inside an organization or business. It includes tasks such as providing customer support, managing warehouses, handling distribution, and overseeing transportation logistics. The objective of logistics activity is to optimize the flow operations, promote efficiency, minimize costs, and improve customer satisfaction. Logistics activities play a vital role in enterprises, particularly in export-oriented industries, as they enhance competitiveness and profitability. Effective logistics management requires the establishment of logistics plans and strategies, along with the utilization of suitable methodologies and technologies. Through the analysis and optimization of logistics expenses, firms can enhance their financial capacity and overall operational efficiency (Shareef, 2023); (Ptashchenko and Sokhatska, 2022); (Dramaretsk, 2023); (Olha and Kibik, 2023); (Tsou, et al., 2022)

There are no studies specifically focused on air express cargo operators, which are couriers that specialize in air express shipments for importers in commercial organizations in the Philippines. Some studies lack a clear distinction between the manner of transportation used, whether it is via sea or via air. Furthermore, the application of the SERVQUAL model in the courier industry has been limited, as this model is predominantly utilized in sectors such as banking, hotels, automotive, airlines, and other service industries. However, the gap in this study is in the sector and respondents chosen within the industry

Research Questions

This study endeavored to improve the service quality and customer satisfaction of air express cargo operators. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following:

1. How do the respondents assess the quality services of air express cargo operators based on the SERVQUAL dimensions:
 - 1.1 Reliability;
 - 1.2 Responsiveness;
 - 1.3 Assurance;
 - 1.4 Empathy; and
 - 1.5 Tangibility ?
2. How do the respondents assess the level of customer satisfaction of the air express cargo operators in terms of:
 - 2.1 Customer Expectations; and
 - 2.2 Customer Perceptions?
3. Is there any significant relationship between service quality and the level of customer satisfaction among air express cargo operators?
4. What are the challenges in the logistics activities encountered by an air express cargo client in terms of using the air express operator's services?
5. Based on the findings, what logistics activity model can be recommended to enhance the service quality of air express cargo operators?

METHODOLOGY

The researcher employed a descriptive correlational approach. Panda (2023) states that this research methodology use quantitative techniques to offer a thorough depiction of two or more variables and their interconnections. Stratified random sampling was utilized to create the sample for the study under review. This method, which falls under the category of non-probability sampling techniques, selects sample members based on their knowledge, relationships, and expertise in a study topic. This means that the researcher chose the participants based on their desire to engage in the study. Similarly, this technique allows the researcher to gather relevant and meaningful data for addressing the study issue. Sample population was based on Cochran's formula and a total of 116 registered importers in the Bureau of Customs at Region VI specifically in Iloilo and 91 sample size shall be considered as respondents for the study. To obtain reliable and valid information, the researcher used a modified self-made survey questionnaire and guide

questions validated by the experts. The questionnaire was tested for internal consistency reliability using the Cronbach's coefficient SPSS. For data interpretation, the researcher should use descriptive correlations. The following statistical instruments were utilized: Ranking, percentage and frequency of the challenges in logistics activities encountered by an air express operator's cargo client. For analyzing the responses and assigning numerical values to each category on the Likert scale. The researcher can then calculate the mean to determine the overall satisfaction level of the respondents and service quality. Lastly, Pearson r correlation test was used to test the relationship among the variables of this study.

For determining the suitability of the tool and avoiding issues related to unclear wording and too long survey administration, a pretest was done prior to the actual distribution of the survey sheet. 25 people who work in importers or importer representatives were chosen to take the pre-test.

The study focused on the following dimensions of service quality: reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibility, as well as customer satisfaction, in terms of customers' expectations and their perceptions of air express cargo operators. Furthermore, the logistics activities under study were limited to pick up and collection, transportation preparation, and customer service and feedback. This study was conducted in Western Visayas, specifically in Iloilo City and Iloilo Province. The respondents were selected by a designated company representative and consisted of importers or their representatives who directly transact with the Bureau of Customs-Iloilo. The survey was covered during the period of the third quarter of 2024.

RESULTS

Table 1

Quality services of air express cargo operators based on the SERVQUAL dimensions

SERVQUAL Dimensions	Mean	Interpretation
A. Reliability	3.635	Very Important
B. Responsiveness	3.622	Very Important
C. Assurance	3.631	Very Important
D. Empathy	3.607	Very Important
E. Tangibility	3.396	Very Important
Composite Mean	3.578	Very Important

Legend: 3.26-4.00 Very Important; 2.51-3.25 Important; 1.76-2.50 Not Important; 1:00-1:75 Very Unimportant

Table 1 presents an assessment of the quality of services based on SERVQUAL Dimensions. Respondents highlight the significance of reliability, evidenced by the highest mean score of 3.635, categorized as "Very Important." According to Mendoza et al. (2023) reliability is the paramount characteristic of service quality that influences the customer. This may lead the researcher to conclude that reliability is a pertinent factor that enhances customer satisfaction among respondents, as the items dispatched by courier are urgent in nature; thus, the prompt receipt of these items significantly influences their satisfaction with the purchasing and couriership process.

The lowest mean score of 3.396 was seen for tangibility categorized as "Very Important.". The SERVQUAL model, which encompasses tangibility alongside reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy, has been effectively utilized to assess service quality perceptions, revealing that tangible factors often correlate strongly with overall customer satisfaction (Ekowati, 2023),(Tang et al., 2022).

The overall evaluation of service quality according to SERVQUAL Dimensions results in a mean value of 3.578, which is qualitatively classified as "Very Important.". In the study of Magdalena and Marek (2023) they asserted that the SERVQUAL characteristics critical for courier services encompass reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibility, which together evaluate the anticipated and perceived quality of logistics services. Aulia et al. (2023) stated that service quality is crucial for the success of service organizations today, as it enhances client loyalty and demonstrates the company's dedication to its operations. For a service-oriented firm, it is essential to continually assess client needs and preferences while endeavoring to fulfill their expectations.

The findings of this study suggest several practical implications for courier services seeking to improve their service quality. First, reliability should remain a primary focus, as it is clearly the most important factor for customers. Ensuring that deliveries are made on time and in good condition can significantly enhance the overall customer experience. Second, while tangibility is less important than reliability, it should not be overlooked. Investing in the professional appearance of delivery personnel, improving packaging, and enhancing the overall service environment can positively impact customer perceptions. Lastly, the other SERVQUAL dimensions—responsiveness, assurance, and empathy—should also be continuously evaluated and improved to ensure that customers feel valued and supported throughout the service process.

In conclusion, this study reinforced the critical role of service quality in customer satisfaction and loyalty. Courier services, like any service-oriented organization, must prioritize customer needs and expectations to stay competitive and thrive in an increasingly demanding market. By focusing on the key SERVQUAL dimensions—reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibility—service providers can enhance the overall quality of their offerings and build stronger, more lasting relationships with their customers.

Table 2

Quality services of air express cargo operators based on the SERVQUAL dimensions in terms of reliability

Reliability	Mean	Interpretation
1 AECO services offer a committed customer service.	3.582	Very Important
2 Promptly deliver the deliverance in a timely manner.	3.626	Very Important
3 Ensure that the tracking status of my shipment is promptly updated and communicated to the customer.	3.714	Very Important
4 Provide notification or make a phone call upon arrival at the residence to deliver a package .	3.604	Very Important
5 Consistently delivers its service with precision.	3.648	Very Important
Composite Mean	3.635	Very Important

Legend: 3.26-4.00 Very Important; 2.51-3.25 Important; 1.76-2.50 Not Important; 1:00-1:75 Very Unimportant

Table 2 presents an assessment of the quality of services in terms of reliability. Respondents emphasized the importance of promptly updating and communicating the tracking status of shipments to customers, as reflected by the highest mean score of 3.714 "Very Important". According to Dandan (2019) timely updates and communication on tracking status are essential, as they boost customer happiness, conform to Must-be Quality, and cultivate trust in logistics services, so elevating total service quality.

Conversely, the lowest mean score of 3.582, categorized as "Very Important," was noted for AECO services offer a committed customer service. According to Marcysiak (2021) dedicated customer service in courier services promotes reliability, fulfills client expectations, and cultivates enduring connections. Furthermore, dedicated customer service in courier operations is essential as it immediately impacts conflict resolution, customer happiness, and eventually cultivates enduring customer loyalty, hence increasing the brand's reputation and commercial stability (Arumugam et al., 2020).

Overall, the evaluation of service quality regarding reliability results in a mean value of 3.635, which is qualitatively classified as "Very Important." According to Qi et al. (2022), reliability profoundly impacts consumer satisfaction with courier services by guaranteeing constant and trustworthy delivery, essential for fostering client confidence and loyalty. Furthermore, reliability is essential in the quality of courier services, as it guarantees prompt and precise delivery, which directly affects customer satisfaction and loyalty, hence improving competitive advantage in the marketplace (Hamidin and Henrayati, 2022).

Table 3 presents an assessment of the quality of services in terms of responsiveness. Respondents emphasized the accuracy and reliability in delivering the

correct and accurate parcels, as reflected by the highest mean score of 3.670 "Very Important". According to Chaudhary and Singh (2024) accurate parcel delivery is crucial to prevent financial losses, enhance customer satisfaction, and improve quality control, ultimately boosting operational efficiency in the logistics and shipping industry. Results revealed that the Implications include less cargo loss and improved quality control. Moreover, Accuracy and reliability in parcel delivery enhance customer satisfaction, reduce operational costs, and improve service efficiency, ultimately fostering trust and loyalty in the courier service (Arikan et al, 2023).

Table 3

Quality services of air express cargo operators based on the SERVQUAL dimensions in terms of responsiveness

Responsiveness	Mean	Interpretation
1. Efficiency of the AECO.	3.549	Very Important
2. Readiness to assist consumers in resolving any issues that may arise.	3.626	Very Important
3. Efficiency in response to consumer inquiries.	3.626	Very Important
4. Availability to provide customer care to consumers.	3.637	Very Important
5. The accuracy and reliability in delivering the correct and accurate parcels.	3.670	Very Important
Composite Mean	3.622	Very Important

Legend: 3.26-4.00 Very Important; 2.51-3.25 Important; 1.76-2.50 Not Important; 1.00-1.75 Very Unimportant.

In contrast, the lowest mean score of 3.549 "Very Important" was recorded for efficiency of the AECO. Courier efficiency is crucial for optimizing last-mile delivery, reducing costs, and improving service quality, ultimately enhancing customer satisfaction and operational effectiveness in the courier industry. Optimized routes and times reduced after analysis (He, et al., 2023). Overall, the evaluation of service quality regarding responsiveness results in a mean score of 3.622, which is qualitatively classified as "Very Important." Kania (2023) asserts that responsiveness profoundly influences service quality in courier services, as adept management of consumer complaints on social media bolsters brand trust and cultivates customer loyalty.

In conclusion, the assessment of service quality in terms of responsiveness revealed that accuracy and reliability in parcel delivery are paramount to customer satisfaction, while operational efficiency remains an important but secondary factor. The study reinforced the need for courier services to focus on both accuracy and responsiveness to enhance service quality and build customer loyalty. The findings also suggest that while operational efficiency is important for reducing costs and improving service delivery times, it should not come at the expense of reliability and customer satisfaction. By prioritizing both the technical and interpersonal aspects of service delivery,

courier services can meet and exceed customer expectations, strengthen brand loyalty, and ensure long-term success in the competitive logistics and shipping industry.

Table 4

Quality services of air express cargo operators based on the SERVQUAL dimensions in terms of assurance

Assurance	Mean	Interpretation
1. Politeness and courteous of the delivery man.	3.538	Very Important
2. Sense of security with the delivery man.	3.703	Very Important
3. Knowledgeable and well-informed and capable of addressing customer problems.	3.659	Very Important
4. Trustworthy of the delivery man	3.681	Very Important
5. Delivery man's professionalism when personal interactions.	3.571	Very Important
Composite Mean	3.631	Very Important

Legend: 3.26-4.00 Very Important; 2.51-3.25 Important; 1.76-2.50 Not Important; 1.00-1.75 Very Unimportant

Table 4 presents an assessment of the quality of services in terms of assurance. Respondents emphasized the sense of security with the delivery man, as reflected by the highest mean score of 3.703 "Very Important". Muda et al. (2023) asserted that a sense of security for delivery people is essential as it cultivates trust, improves job performance, and alleviates conflicts stemming from customer dissatisfaction in transactions, especially inside COD systems.

Conversely, the lowest mean score of 3.538, categorized as "Very Important," was attributed to the politeness and courtesy of the delivery personnel. Firdaus et al (2023) asserted that politeness among delivery staff improves customer satisfaction, cultivates positive relationships, and enriches the whole experience, consistent with the tenets of effective customer-agent interactions. The study by Marcysiak (2021) indicates that the politeness and respect of delivery professionals boost client satisfaction, hence building positive connections and trust, which are essential for customer retention in the competitive courier services industry.

Overall, the evaluation of service quality regarding assurance results in a mean score of 3.631, which is qualitatively classified as "Very Important." Gulc (2021) asserted that assurance is essential in courier service quality, as it cultivates trust and confidence among e-customers, hence impacting their overall happiness and perception of service reliability. Moreover, assurance in service quality is essential for courier services, as it cultivates client trust, improves perceived safety, and guarantees reliability in adhering to delivery timeframes and preserving product integrity (Marcysiak, 2021).

Table 5

As Quality services of air express cargo operators based on the SERVQUAL dimensions in terms of empathy

Empathy	Mean	Interpretation
1. Customer care provided is attentive and considerate towards their consumers	3.582	Very Important
2. Provides personalized attention by the courier	3.560	Very Important
3. Service is cognizant of the clients' needs	3.615	Very Important
4. Effective communication with the deliveryman and customer support crucial in resolving delivery	3.626	Very Important
5. The availability of client assistance consistently.	3.648	Very Important
Composite Mean	3.607	Very Important

Legend: 3.26-4.00 Very Important; 2.51-3.25 Important; 1.76-2.50 Not Important; 1:00-1:75 Very Unimportant

Table 5 presents an assessment of the quality of services in terms of empathy. Respondents emphasized the availability of client assistance consistently, as reflected by the highest mean score of 3.648 "Very Important" Consistent client support improved interaction quality, hence positively affecting total customer happiness in the courier service sector, as demonstrated by the mediating function of interaction quality in the research (Bae and Kim, 2024). Furthermore, regular client support in courier services improved customer experience, cultivates positive relationships, and directly impacts service quality, as indicated in the relational model established in the study (Gulc, 2021)

Conversely, the lowest mean score of 3.560, categorized as "Very Important," was attributed to provides personalized attention by the courier. Customized attention fosters a favorable customer experience, which is essential for contentment. Research demonstrated that personalized service by couriers enhances client happiness, thereby cultivating loyalty (Huang, 2023). Customers value the recognition and fulfillment of their individual demands, fostering a sense of appreciation and attentiveness. Overall, the evaluation of service quality regarding empathy results in a mean score of 3.607, which is qualitatively classified as "Very Important." The research conducted by Tang et al. (2022) and Qi et al. (2022) indicate that empathy is the paramount factor affecting customer happiness in courier services, underscoring its essential contribution to improving overall service quality and customer experience. Moreover, empathy substantially improves service quality in courier services by cultivating client trust and happiness, resulting in enhanced relationships and loyalty through the effective understanding and resolving of customer demands (Atik and Ekowati, 2023).

However, despite the importance of personalized attention, it appears that customers prioritize consistent availability of support over highly individualized service in the courier sector. This could be because, in the context of logistics, reliability and

immediate assistance are more urgent than tailored experiences. Nonetheless, providing personalized attention, even in small ways, can significantly contribute to a customer's sense of being valued and understood. This personalized approach can increase customer loyalty and contribute to a more favorable brand perception in the long term. Personalized attention, while still important, is viewed as slightly less critical but can still contribute significantly to customer happiness when implemented effectively. Empathy, as a whole, emerges as a key driver of service quality, contributing to the establishment of trust, positive relationships, and customer loyalty. By continually focusing on improving empathetic interactions—whether through responsive support or personalized attention—courier services can enhance the overall customer experience, fostering long-term satisfaction and business success.

Table 6

Quality services of air express cargo operators based on the SERVQUAL dimensions in terms of tangibility.

Tangibility	Mean	Interpretation
1. Attire of the delivery personnel	3.220	Important
2. Type of vehicles utilized	3.440	Very Important
3. Modern appearance of the equipment	3.363	Very Important
4. User-friendly interface of the AECOs computer program	3.593	Very Important
5. Contemporary appearance and ambiance of the AECO offices	3.363	Very Important
Composite Mean	3.396	Very Important

Legend: 3.26-4.00 Very Important; 2.51-3.25 Important; 1.76-2.50 Not Important; 1.75-1:00 Very Unimportant

Table 6 presents an assessment of the quality of services in terms of tangibility. Respondents emphasized the user-friendly interface of the AECOs computer program, as reflected by the highest mean score of 3.593 "Very Important". Lin et al. (2024) asserted that a user-friendly interface in courier applications boosts operational efficiency, facilitates intuitive navigation, and improves user happiness, hence resulting in superior performance in logistics management. Similarly, an intuitive interface improves user acceptance and efficiency in the courier management system, enabling easier navigation, faster data retrieval, and an enhanced overall customer experience (Regla and Perea, 2022). Furthermore, Zhao et al. (2022) asserted that a user-friendly interface in a courier application improves user engagement and satisfaction.

Conversely, the lowest mean score of 3.22, categorized as "Important," was attributed to the attire of the delivery personnel. According to Johnston et al. (2023), attire is essential for delivery people as it conveys legitimacy and fosters a sense of belonging

within consumers' surroundings, hence influencing their acceptability and safety during service delivery.

Overall, the evaluation of service quality regarding tangibility results in a mean score of 3.396, which is qualitatively classified as "Very Important." According to Solano et al. (2023) tangibility greatly impacts client perceptions by improving physical presentation and aesthetics, which are essential for fostering trust and satisfaction in service quality within the courier industry. Furthermore, Yoganandan, et al. (2022) asserted that tangibility substantially affects customer loyalty in logistics, as it includes physical elements that improve perceived service quality, thus cultivating trust and contentment among clients.

Table 7

Level of customer satisfaction of selected air express cargo operators in terms of customer expectations

SERVQUAL Dimensions	Mean	Interpretation
A. Reliability	3.169	Satisfied
B. Responsiveness	3.158	Satisfied
C. Assurance	3.233	Satisfied
D. Empathy	3.262	Very Satisfied
E. Tangibility	3.143	Satisfied
Composite Mean	3.578	Satisfied

Legend: 3.26-4.00 Very Satisfied, 2.51-3.25 Satisfied; 1.76-2.50 Slightly Satisfied; 1.00-1.75 Not Satisfied

Table 7 presents the level of customer satisfaction based on customer expectations. Respondents emphasize the importance of empathy, as reflected by the highest mean score of 3.262 "Very Satisfied". For instance, a study found that empathy emerged as the most significant factor affecting satisfaction, highlighting its importance in customer interactions (Tang et al., 2022).

In contrast, the lowest mean score of 3.143 was recorded for tangibility "Satisfied". Overall, the level of customer satisfaction based on customer expectations yields a mean value of 3.193, which is qualitatively interpreted as "Satisfied".

According to Javier et al. (2023), the study identified all SERVQUAL dimensions—tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy—as strongly impacting customer satisfaction, underscoring their critical role in fulfilling customer expectations in service delivery. Moreover, Fransiska et al. (2023) indicated that the SERVQUAL dimensions pertinent to courier services encompass reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibility, which jointly evaluate service quality in relation to client expectations within this domain. The study's results indicate that superior service quality surpasses customer expectations. While there are areas like tangibility that may require further attention, the overall performance across these dimensions helps fulfill a

wide range of customer needs, ensuring that most customers are satisfied with the services provided.

In conclusion, the level of customer satisfaction within the courier service sector, as based on customer expectations, showed that empathy and other relational factors are key drivers of satisfaction, while tangible aspects such as the professionalism of staff and the condition of delivery vehicles are important but secondary in comparison. The overall satisfaction score of 3.193 suggested that while customers are generally pleased with the service they receive, there are areas for improvement, particularly in the tangible aspects of the service. To enhance customer satisfaction further, courier services should continue to focus on improving their empathetic interactions, responsiveness, and reliability, while also addressing the physical aspects of service delivery, such as staff presentation and vehicle condition.

Table 8

Level of customer satisfaction of selected air express cargo operators in terms Customer Expectations

Reliability	Mean	Interpretation
1 AECO services offer a committed customer service.	3.154	Satisfied
2 Promptly deliver the deliverance in a timely manner.	3.143	Satisfied
3 Ensure that the tracking status of my shipment is promptly updated and communicated to the customer.	3.165	Satisfied
4 Provide notification or make a phone call upon arrival at the residence to deliver a package .	3.187	Satisfied
5 Consistently delivers its service with precision.	3.198	Satisfied
Composite Mean	3.169	Satisfied

Legend: 3.26-4.00 Very Satisfied; 2.51-3.25 Satisfied; 1.76-2.50 Slightly Satisfied; 1:75-1:00 Not Satisfied

Table 8 presents the level of customer satisfaction in terms of customer expectation based on reliability. Respondents emphasized that they consistently deliver their service with precision, as reflected by the highest mean score of 3.198 "Satisfied". In the study of Bae and Kim (2024) enhanced expectation-performance alignment in service delivery results in superior outcome quality, favorably impacting total customer satisfaction within the courier service sector. The accuracy of delivery services enhances consumer value, resulting in increased user satisfaction, as demonstrated by the study's findings regarding courier service elements (Lee, 2023).

The lowest mean score of 3.154, indicating "Satisfied," was obtained. AECO services provide dedicated customer service. Marcysiak (2021) asserted that dedicated

customer service in courier services promotes reliability, fulfills client expectations, and cultivates enduring connections, hence contributing to competitive advantage and customer satisfaction in a saturated market. Furthermore, dedicated customer service in couriers is essential as it immediately impacts conflict resolution, customer happiness, and eventually cultivates enduring customer loyalty, hence increasing the brand's reputation and commercial stability (Arumugam et al., 2020).

The overall consumer satisfaction for expectation on based reliability has a mean value of 3.169, which is qualitatively classified as "Satisfied." Reliability in service quality denotes the consistent capacity to fulfill client expectations, profoundly impacting customer satisfaction and promoting favorable word-of-mouth communication (Okan, 2023). Moreover, Qi et al. (2022) asserted that reliability substantially impacts customer satisfaction in courier services, meeting expectations through consistent and dependable service delivery, as emphasized in the study's results.

Table 9

Level of customer satisfaction of selected air express cargo operators in terms Customer Expectations

Responsiveness	Mean	Interpretation
1. Efficiency of the AECO.	3.143	Satisfied
2. Readiness to assist consumers in resolving any issues that may arise.	3.121	Satisfied
3. Efficiency in response to consumer inquiries.	3.132	Satisfied
4. Availability to provide customer care to consumers.	3.176	Satisfied
5. The accuracy and reliability in delivering the correct and accurate parcels.	3.220	Satisfied
Composite Mean	3.158	Satisfied

Legend: 3.26-4.00 Very Satisfied; 2.51-3.25 Satisfied; 1.76-2.50 Slightly Satisfied; 1.75-1.00 Not Satisfied

Table 9 presents the level of customer satisfaction in terms of customer expectation based on responsiveness. Respondents emphasized the accuracy and reliability in delivering the correct and accurate parcels, as reflected by the highest mean score of 3.220 "Satisfied". As per Chaudhary and Singh (2024), precise parcel delivery is essential to avert financial losses, augment client satisfaction, and enhance quality control, hence increasing operational efficiency in the logistics and shipping sector. The findings indicate that the implications encompass reduced cargo loss and enhanced quality control. Furthermore, precision and dependability in parcel delivery augment client satisfaction, decrease operational expenses, and promote service efficiency, ultimately cultivating trust and loyalty in the courier business (Arikan et al., 2023).

The lowest mean score reported was 3.121. Willingness to aid consumers in addressing any problems that may occur. The study by Arumugam et al. (2020) highlighted that successful dispute resolution markedly improves customer satisfaction, suggesting that a willingness to address concerns is essential for sustaining consumer loyalty in courier services. The study highlighted that enhancing courier satisfaction via dynamic operating regions might improve retention and loyalty, so indirectly addressing consumer concerns regarding delivery performance (Aud et al., 2023). The overall customer satisfaction for responsiveness to expectations has a mean value of 3.158, which is qualitatively characterized as "Satisfied." Elevated client satisfaction in expedited delivery systems is attained by dynamically adjusting courier territories, improving responsiveness, and sustaining service performance indicators via optimal work allocations (Kiok, 2023).

In conclusion, the findings of this study revealed that customer satisfaction with courier services, particularly in terms of responsiveness, is primarily driven by the accuracy and reliability of parcel delivery. While customers are generally satisfied with these aspects, as indicated by the highest mean score for accuracy, there is still a need for improvement in the responsiveness to customer concerns, as shown by the lowest mean score for willingness to assist customers. To further enhance customer satisfaction, courier services should focus on not only maintaining accuracy and reliability but also improving the responsiveness of customer service, particularly in resolving issues and addressing customer inquiries promptly.

Table 10

Level of customer satisfaction of selected air express cargo operators towards assurance in terms of Customer Expectations

Assurance	Mean	Interpretation
1. Politeness and courteous of the delivery man.	3.165	Satisfied
2. Sense of security with the delivery man.	3.286	Satisfied
3. Knowledgeable and well-informed and capable of addressing customer problems.	3.220	Satisfied
4. Trustworthy of the delivery man	3.242	Satisfied
5. Delivery man's professionalism when personal interactions.	3.253	Satisfied
Composite Mean	3.233	Satisfied

Legend: 3.26-4.00 Very Satisfied; 2.51-3.25 Satisfied; 1.76-2.50 Slightly Satisfied; 1.75-1.00 Not Satisfied

Table 10 presents the level of customer satisfaction in terms of customer expectation based on assurance. Respondents emphasize Sense of security with the delivery man., as reflected by the highest mean score of 3.286 "Very Satisfied". Muda et al. (2023) asserted that a sense of security for delivery people is essential as it cultivates

trust, improves job performance, and alleviates conflicts stemming from client dissatisfaction in transactions, especially in cash-on-delivery systems.

The lowest mean score of 3.165 was obtained. The delivery man's politeness and courtesy. According to Firdaus, et al. (2023) politeness among delivery staff improves customer satisfaction, cultivates positive relationships, and enriches the whole experience, consistent with the tenets of effective customer-agent interactions. The study by Marcysiak (2021) indicates that the politeness and respect of delivery professionals boost client satisfaction, hence building positive connections and trust, which are essential for customer retention in the competitive courier services industry.

The overall customer satisfaction regarding expectation-based assurance has a mean value of 3.233, understood qualitatively as "Satisfied." Assurance, defined by employee expertise and politeness, profoundly impacts customer satisfaction by synchronizing service delivery with customer expectations in the courier industry, as indicated in the study by Solano, et al. (2023). The research demonstrated that assurance substantially affects customer satisfaction, indicating that fulfilling consumer expectations regarding service quality is essential for satisfaction in courier services (Nuriyah et al., 2023).

Table 11

Level of customer satisfaction of selected air express cargo operators towards empathy in terms of Customer Expectations

Empathy	Mean	Interpretation
1. Customer care provided is attentive and considerate towards their consumers	3.275	Satisfied
2. Provides personalized attention by the courier	3.242	Satisfied
3. Service is cognizant of the clients' needs	3.330	Very Satisfied
4. Effective communication with the deliveryman and customer support crucial in resolving delivery	3.242	Satisfied
5. The availability of client assistance consistently.	3.220	Satisfied
Composite Mean	3.262	Very Satisfied

Legend: 3.26-4.00 Very Satisfied; 2.51-3.25 Satisfied; 1.76-2.50 Slightly Satisfied; 1.75-1.00 Not Satisfied

Table 11 presents the level of customer satisfaction in terms of customer expectation based on empathy. Respondents emphasize service is cognizant of the clients' needs, as reflected by the highest mean score of 3.330 "Very Satisfied". According to Ilkme (2024) service organizations that comprehend and address client requirements improve customer happiness, cultivating loyalty through efficient service provision,

prompt product delivery, and clear billing methods. Empathy profoundly impacts customer happiness in courier services, underscoring the necessity of comprehending and fulfilling clients' demands efficiently (Tang et al., 2020).

Conversely, the lowest mean score of 3.220 was noted for the consistent availability of client assistance. Consistent client support meets customer expectations by reinforcing positive experiences, therefore improving satisfaction and loyalty through effective management of expected service standards. Moreover, a greater alignment between expectations and performance in client support substantially impacts outcome quality, hence improving overall customer satisfaction in the courier service sector (Bae and Kim, 2024).

The overall customer satisfaction regarding expectations based on empathy has a mean value of 3.262, which is qualitatively characterized as "Satisfied." Empathy profoundly influences customer satisfaction by aligning service performance with customer expectations, hence enhancing the total Customer Satisfaction Index in courier services.

Table 12

Level of customer satisfaction of selected air express cargo operators towards tangibility in terms of Customer Expectations

Tangibility	Mean	Interpretation
1. Attire of the delivery personnel	3.099	Satisfied
2. Type of vehicles utilized	3.198	Satisfied
3. Modern appearance of the equipment	3.132	Very Satisfied
4. User-friendly interface of the AECOs computer program	3.110	Satisfied
5. Contemporary appearance and ambiance of the AECO offices	3.176	Satisfied
Composite Mean	3.143	Satisfied

Legend: 3.26-4.00 Very Satisfied; 2.51-3.25 Satisfied; 1.76-2.50 Slightly Satisfied; 1.75-1.00 Not Satisfied

Table 12 presents the level of customer satisfaction in terms of customer expectation based on tangibility. Respondents emphasized Type of vehicles utilized, as reflected by the highest mean score of 3.198 "Satisfied". The report underscores that consumer expectations affect the choice of autonomous cars, highlighting efficiency, reliability, and adaptability in parcel delivery operations to improve overall satisfaction (Mohammad et al. 2022). Moreover, contemporary courier firms are progressively investing in hybrid and electric cars to fulfill client expectations about environmental considerations and safety, so augmenting their reputation and corporate social responsibility (Marcysiak, 2021).

Conversely, the lowest mean score of 3.099 was seen for the attire of the delivery staff. Employee uniforms shape consumer views, resulting in increased attribution of accountability to the organization and potentially impacting customer satisfaction in relation to service quality standards. Uniforms can influence consumer perceptions of service quality, as uniformed staff provoke heightened attributions of accountability to the organization (Smith et al., 2020).

The overall customer satisfaction regarding expectations based on tangibility has a mean value of 3.143, which is qualitatively characterized as "Satisfied" (Enya et al., (2023). Customer satisfaction about tangibility is assessed positively ($\beta=0.577$), suggesting that expectations are fulfilled, however there remains potential for enhancement in this area. Tangibility profoundly affects customer happiness by influencing perceptions of service quality, as customers assess their experiences relative to expectations established by observable elements of the service (Solano-Salono et al., 2023).

In conclusion, the assessment of customer satisfaction based on tangibility highlighted that the physical elements of courier service play a significant role in shaping customer expectations and overall satisfaction. While customers are generally satisfied with the type of vehicles used by courier companies, with the highest mean score of 3.198, there is still room for improvement in other areas, such as the attire of delivery staff, which received a lower mean score of 3.099. This suggests that while the physical aspects of the service are largely meeting customer expectations, certain details, such as staff uniforms, could be enhanced to improve perceptions of professionalism and service quality.

Table 13 presents the level of customer satisfaction based on customer perceptions. Respondents emphasized the importance of assurance, as reflected by the highest mean score of 3.389 "Very Satisfied". In contrast, the lowest mean score of 3.310 "Very Satisfied" was recorded for tangibility. Overall, the assessment of service quality based on SERVQUAL Dimensions yields a mean value of 3.311, which is qualitatively interpreted as "Very Satisfied"

Table 13

Level of customer satisfaction of selection air express cargo in terms of customer perceptions.

SERVQUAL Dimension	Mean	Interpretation
A. Reliability	3.264	Very Satisfied
B. Responsiveness	3.273	Very Satisfied
C. Assurance	3.389	Very Satisfied
D. Empathy	3.321	Very Satisfied
E. Tangibility	3.310	Very Satisfied
Composite Mean	3.311	Very Satisfied

Legend: 3.26-4.00 Very Satisfied, 2.51-3.25 Satisfied; 1.76-2.50 Slightly Satisfied; 1.00-1.75 Not Satisfied

German et al. (2022) asserted that the SERVQUAL dimensions substantially impact client perceptions in courier services, influencing satisfaction and loyalty through reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibility amid the COVID-19 pandemic. Furthermore, Salamah et al. (2022) underscores that elements of service quality substantially affect consumer views in the courier sector, influencing total satisfaction and retention rates. The findings indicate that service quality has a favorable impact on customer satisfaction.

In the highly competitive courier industry, where customer expectations are ever-increasing, maintaining a high level of service quality across all SERVQUAL dimensions is essential. By focusing on improving both relational aspects, such as assurance and empathy, and tangible elements like staff appearance and vehicle condition, courier services can strengthen their customer satisfaction levels, enhance brand reputation, and secure a loyal customer base for the future.

Table 14

Level of customer satisfaction of selected air express cargo operators towards reliability in terms of Customer Perception

Reliability	Mean	Interpretation
1 AECO services offer a committed customer service.	3.253	Satisfied
2 Promptly deliver the deliverance in a timely manner.	3.286	Very Satisfied
3 Ensure that the tracking status of my shipment is promptly updated and communicated to the customer.	3.231	Satisfied
4 Provide notification or make a phone call upon arrival at the residence to deliver a package .	3.242	Satisfied
5 Consistently delivers its service with precision.	3.308	Very Satisfied
Composite Mean	3.264	Very Satisfied

Legend: 3.26-4.00 Very Satisfied; 2.51-3.25 Satisfied; 1.76-2.50 Slightly Satisfied; 1.75-1.00 Not Satisfied

Table 14 presents the level of customer satisfaction in terms of customer perception based on reliability. Respondents emphasized the Consistently delivers its service with precision. as reflected by the highest mean score of 3.308 “Very Satisfied”. Respondents emphasize the importance of delivery accuracy and the ability to resolve issues promptly, suggesting that constant service precision is essential for fulfilling the expectations of both buyers and sellers in the courier industry. Purchasers and vendors choose service excellence over shipping expenses (Timotius et al., 2023). The study indicates that courier satisfaction is improved by dynamic working zones, facilitating effective service delivery while fulfilling elevated service standards in rapid delivery systems (Auad et al. ,2023).

Conversely, the lowest mean score of 3.231 “Satisfied” was reflected. It was seen that to ensure that the tracking status of my shipment is promptly updated and communicated to the customer. According to Yawalkar (2024) real-time tracking updates and automated messages concerning shipment status substantially improve customer perception by offering transparency and timely information during the delivery process. Moreover, real-time GPS tracking and environmental monitoring augment customer perception by delivering precise, timely updates regarding cargo status, position, and condition, thereby enhancing communication and confidence (Sumitra et al., 2023).

The overall customer satisfaction regarding reliability has a mean value of 3.264, which is qualitatively classified as "Very Positive." Taylor (2024) states that reliability profoundly impacts customer satisfaction, as consistent and trustworthy service cultivates favorable opinions, resulting in increased overall satisfaction and loyalty among customers.

Table 15

Level of customer satisfaction of selected air express cargo operators towards responsiveness in terms of Customer Perception

Responsiveness	Mean	Interpretation
1. Efficiency of the AECO.	3.242	Satisfied
2. Readiness to assist consumers in resolving any issues that may arise.	3.297	Very Satisfied
3. Efficiency in response to consumer inquiries.	3.297	Very Satisfied
4. Availability to provide customer care to consumers.	3.220	Satisfied
5. The accuracy and reliability in delivering the correct and accurate parcels.	3.308	Very Satisfied
Composite Mean	3.273	Very Satisfied

Legend: 3.26-4.00 Very Satisfied; 2.51-3.25 Satisfied; 1.76-2.50 Slightly Satisfied; 1.75-1.00 Not Satisfied

Table 15 presents the level of customer satisfaction in terms of customer perception based on responsiveness. Respondents emphasized the accuracy and reliability in delivering the correct and accurate parcels. as reflected by the highest mean score of 3.308” Very Satisfied”. According Ngali et al. (2019) responsiveness greatly impacts customer satisfaction, highlighting the necessity of precision and dependability in the delivery of accurate shipments, as demonstrated by the study's results. Responsiveness profoundly affects customer perception, as respondents emphasize the significance of accuracy and reliability in the prompt delivery of proper goods, hence augmenting total customer satisfaction (Mohd et al, 2020).

Conversely, the lowest mean score of 3.220 was noted for the capacity to deliver customer service to consumers. According to Adi et al. (2024) customer views reveal that

service parameters, particularly the availability of customer support, greatly impact the choice of delivery service providers, receiving a 65.88% importance rating in the study. Moreover, consumer views of interaction justice favorably affect interaction quality, subsequently improving overall happiness, so underscoring the significance of effective customer service in the courier sector (Bae and Kim, 2024).

The overall customer satisfaction regarding responsiveness has a mean score of 3.273, which is qualitatively classified as "Very Positive." The study of Castillo et al. (2023) indicated that customer satisfaction concerning delivery service responsiveness is rated as moderate, with responsiveness recognized as a crucial determinant of overall customer satisfaction. The responsiveness of courier services is strongly linked to customer happiness, suggesting that prompt responses improve consumer contentment and promote ongoing utilization of the services (Pigao, 2023).

In conclusion, responsiveness is a critical determinant of customer satisfaction in the courier service industry, as it significantly influences customer perceptions and overall happiness. The findings highlighted that accuracy, reliability, and prompt delivery of goods are highly valued by customers, as reflected by the highest satisfaction scores. Conversely, areas such as customer service delivery and interaction quality, which received lower satisfaction ratings, underscore opportunities for improvement in meeting customer expectations. Studies emphasize that responsiveness not only enhances consumer satisfaction but also fosters trust, loyalty, and the likelihood of continued use of courier services. To remain competitive and ensure long-term success, courier companies must prioritize precision, dependability, and efficient customer support, as these elements are vital in building strong customer relationships and driving satisfaction in a highly demanding market

Table 16

Level of customer satisfaction of selected air express cargo operators towards assurance in terms of Customer Expectations

Assurance	Mean	Interpretation
1. Politeness and courteous of the delivery man.	3.330	Very Satisfied
2. Sense of security with the delivery man.	3.473	Very Satisfied
3. Knowledgeable and well-informed and capable of addressing customer problems.	3.385	Very Satisfied
4 Trustworthy of the delivery man	3.407	Very Satisfied
.		
5. Delivery man's professionalism when personal interactions.	3.352	Very Satisfied
Composite Mean	3.389	Very Satisfied

Legend: 3.26-4.00 Very Satisfied; 2.51-3.25 Satisfied; 1.76-2.50 Slightly Satisfied; 1.75-1.00 Not Satisfied

Table 16 presents the level of customer satisfaction in terms of customer perception based on assurance. Respondents emphasize the Sense of security with the delivery man. as reflected by the highest mean score of 3.473 “Very Satisfied”. The research demonstrates that security substantially affects customer satisfaction, indicating that respondents prioritize a sense of security with the delivery staff at PT Lion Parcel (Robin and Eyyanto, 2023). The survey reveal that respondents have a considerable sense of security with delivery professionals, underscoring the significance of trust in safeguarding parcel safety during last-mile delivery (Syuhailah et al., 2024).

Conversely, the lowest mean score of 3.330 “Very Satisfied” was noted for the politeness and courtesy of the delivery personnel. Courteous couriers markedly improve client opinion, evidenced by a part-worth coefficient of 0.219, underscoring the significance of polite conduct in logistics service preferences (Pulupi et al., 2022). Interaction justice favorably affects the assessment of interaction quality, suggesting that the politeness and civility of delivery people improve customer satisfaction in the courier service sector (Bae and Kim, 2024).

The overall customer satisfaction for assurance perception has a mean score of 3.389, qualitatively characterized as "Very Positive." The research indicates that views of justice enhance interaction quality, thereby impacting overall customer happiness, so underscoring the significance of assurance in service provision (Pulupi et al, 2022). Empathy, a crucial feature of service quality, profoundly impacts customer happiness, indicating that the politeness and courtesy of delivery staff enhance client views in courier services (Tang et al.,2022).

Table 17

Level of customer satisfaction of selected air express cargo operators towards empathy in terms of Customer Perception.

Empathy	Mean	Interpretation
1. Customer care provided is attentive and considerate towards their consumers	3.275	Very Satisfied
2. Provides personalized attention by the courier	3.319	Very Satisfied
3. Service is cognizant of the clients' needs	3.297	Very Satisfied
4. Effective communication with the deliveryman and customer support crucial in resolving delivery	3.396	Very Satisfied
5. The availability of client assistance consistently.	3.319	Very Satisfied
Composite Mean	3.321	Very Satisfied

Legend: 3.26-4.00 Very Satisfied; 2.51-3.25 Satisfied; 1.76-2.50 Slightly Satisfied; 1.75-1.00 Not Satisfied

Table 17 presents the level of customer satisfaction in terms of customer perception based on empathy. Respondents emphasized the Effective communication with the deliveryman and customer support crucial in resolving delivery. as reflected by the highest mean score of 3.396” Very Satisfied”. According Eko and Midia (2024) effective communication with delivery staff and customer assistance is crucial for reducing delivery delays, improving customer perception, and augmenting overall service satisfaction in food delivery services. Moreover, effective communication with delivery workers and customer support substantially impacts customer perception and satisfaction in the courier sector, as seen by the positive correlation between customer service and satisfaction (Sule, 2024). Effective communication with delivery people and customer support profoundly impacts customer perception, hence improving the overall customer experience and satisfaction in B2B express delivery services (Cepeda-Carrión et al., 2023).

Conversely, the lowest mean score of 3.275 “Very Satisfied” was noted for the attentiveness and consideration of customer care delivered to consumers. The research emphasized that the demeanor of couriers substantially affects client satisfaction, suggesting that attentive and thoughtful customer service is essential for favorable consumer views in logistics services (Palupi et al., 2022). Empathy, a crucial factor of service excellence, profoundly impacts clients' opinions of courier services, augmenting their pleasure and loyalty through attentive and caring care (Taylor, 2024).

The overall customer satisfaction level, based on empathy perception, has a mean value of 3.321, which is qualitatively classified as "Very Positive". Empathy profoundly impacts customer satisfaction in courier services by improving customer perception and cultivating a deeper emotional bond, resulting in elevated overall satisfaction levels (Tang et al., 2022). Empathy profoundly impacts customer happiness in courier services, demonstrating a robust link that suggests clients prioritize understanding and responsiveness in their service encounters (Castillo et. al, 2023). This robust link between empathy and satisfaction underscores that customers place a high value on service providers who demonstrate understanding, care, and responsiveness during interactions.

To sustain customer loyalty and competitive advantage, courier companies must prioritize fostering empathetic service interactions, focusing on effective communication, attentiveness, and genuine care for customer needs. By doing so, they can not only elevate overall customer satisfaction but also strengthen emotional bonds and long-term trust, which are critical for success in a highly competitive and customer-centric industry.

Table 18
Level of customer satisfaction of selected air express cargo operators towards tangibility in terms of Customer Perception

Tangibility	Mean	Interpretation
1. Attire of the delivery personnel	3.275	Very Satisfied
2. Type of vehicles utilized	3.363	Very Satisfied

3. Modern appearance of the equipment	3.319	Very Satisfied
4. User-friendly interface of the AECOs computer program	3.275	Very Satisfied
5. Contemporary appearance and ambiance of the AECO offices	3.319	Very Satisfied
Composite Mean	3.310	Very Satisfied

Legend: 3.26-4.00 Very Satisfied; 2.51-3.25 Satisfied; 1.76-2.50 Slightly Satisfied; 1.75-1.00 Not Satisfied

Table 18 presents the level of customer satisfaction in terms of customer perception based on tangibility. Respondents emphasized the Type of vehicles utilized, as reflected by the highest mean score of 3.363 “Very Satisfied”. The research examined drones and automated guided vehicles (AGVs) as novel delivery systems, emphasizing their benefits and drawbacks in relation to conventional courier services and their impact on client views (Koncova et al.,2022). Furthermore, the study of Aulia et al.(2022) where respondents asserted that couriers like passenger motorcycles, especially automated models, for their greater carrying capacity, despite reservations over their appropriateness for courier duties.

The user-friendly interface of the AECOs computer software received the lowest mean score of 3.275 “Very satisfied”. According to Regla and Perea (2022) users strongly concur about the user-friendly interface of the designed courier management system, hence boosting customer perception and overall satisfaction with the service. The survey reveals significant user consensus with the interface of the courier management system, indicating a favorable customer perception of its usability and technological integration (Alfio and Rossian, 2022).

The overall consumer satisfaction for tangibility has a mean value of 3.310, which is qualitatively classified as "Very Positive." According to Taylor (2024) tangibility profoundly affects customer satisfaction in courier services, as clients see physical elements such as packing, delivery vehicles, and staff appearance as benchmarks of overall service excellence. Moreover, the study highlights that customer satisfaction in B2B express delivery is affected by characteristics such as fundamental service experience and critical moments, which include tangible elements (Cepeda-Carrión et al., 2023). Moreover, visual attractiveness negatively influences consumer satisfaction in last-mile delivery, suggesting that tangible elements may detrimentally impact customer perception in courier services (Vrhovac et al., 2024).

Table 19
Relationship between SERVQUAL Dimension and Level of Customer Satisfaction in terms of Customer Expectations

SERVQUAL Dimension		Reliability CE	Decision	Interpretation
Empathy	Pearson	0.966	Reject HO	Significant

Sig(2 tailed)	0.007 *
N	90

Table 19 showed that there is a positive, very high and significant relationship between the assessment of respondents on the empathy of air express cargo operators and the customer's level of satisfaction of reliability in terms of their expectations ($r=0.966$; $p<.05$). The greater the importance of empathy, the higher the level of satisfaction with reliability, as perceived by customers based on their expectations. The rest of the data when group according to the assessment of SERVQUAL dimension of air express cargo operators and customers level of satisfaction in terms of their expectations indicates that there is no significant difference.

According to Widagdo et al. (2023) empathy and reliability substantially impact customer satisfaction, emphasizing the importance of fulfilling customer expectations in these domains to improve overall satisfaction in service delivery. The findings indicated that reliability and empathy exert the most significant impact on customer satisfaction. Furthermore, empathy substantially impacts client satisfaction, while reliability fulfills expectations, enhancing overall satisfaction in courier services, as indicated by the study's findings (Tang et al. 2022).

Empathy is essential for improving client happiness, especially in courier services, where it greatly affects perceptions of reliability. Research demonstrates that empathy and reliability are critical factors influencing consumer satisfaction in many service industries, such as courier and e-commerce delivery services (Tang et al., 2022; Widagdo et al., 2023; Hui et al., 2023). The interaction between employee empathy and client happiness cultivates trust, which is crucial for service loyalty (Bahadur, 2020). This link highlights the need of comprehending client expectations, since elevated perceptions of empathy are associated with enhanced satisfaction about reliability (Widagdo et al., 2023; Hui et al., 2023).

Table 20 showed that there is a positive, very high and significant relationship between the assessment of respondents on the assurance of air express cargo operators and the customer's level satisfaction of assurance in terms of their customer perception ($r=0.913$; $p<0.30$) ; and assessment of respondents on the tangibility of air express cargo operators and the customers level of satisfaction of empathy in terms of their customer perception ($r=0.954$; $p<0.12$).

The significance of assurance correlates positively with customer satisfaction levels, as evidenced by consumer perceptions. According to Bae and Janghyun (2024) greater significance placed on assurance correlates with heightened satisfaction, since assurance positively affects customer views of service quality in the courier sector. Furthermore, the elevated significance attributed to assurance is associated with heightened satisfaction levels, as customers regard assurance as a pivotal factor affecting their overall service quality in courier services (Taylor, 2024).

Table 20

Relationship between SERVQUAL Dimension and Level of Customer Satisfaction in terms of Customer Perception (CP)

SERVQUAL Dimension		Assurance CP	Decision	Interpretation
Assurance	Pearson Sig(2 tailed) N	0.913 0.030 * 90	Reject HO	Significant

SERVQUAL Dimension		Empathy CP	Decision	Interpretation
Tangibility	Pearson Sig(2 tailed) N	0.954 0.012 * 90	Reject HO	Significant

Ultimately, the significance of tangibility correlates positively with consumer satisfaction with empathy. This was corroborated by Qi et al. (2022). The research demonstrated that although tangibility is a dimension of service quality, empathy is recognized as the paramount component affecting customer happiness, indicating a nuanced relationship rather than a direct association. The study revealed a positive correlation between tangibility and empathy; improving tangibility can increase customer happiness, highlighting the importance of both aspects in service delivery (Solano, et al., 2023).

The significance of assurance in courier services profoundly impacts client happiness, as demonstrated by several studies. Assurance, characterized as the confidence and trust clients have in the service provider, is essential alongside other aspects such as reliability and responsiveness (Tang et al., 2022). Studies demonstrate that elevated assurance levels are associated with enhanced customer satisfaction, especially within e-commerce courier services, where elements such as tangibility and reliability further influence consumer views (Pigao, 2023). The expectancy-discrepancy theory posits that alignment between anticipated and actual service quality improves overall satisfaction, with assurance serving as a mediating variable (Bae and Kim, 2024). In expedited delivery systems, sustaining elevated confidence levels is crucial for customer retention and loyalty, particularly due to the competitive market landscape

(Auad et al., 2023). Consequently, augmenting assurance can result in enhanced consumer experiences and contentment within the courier sector (Lee, 2023).

The correlation between tangibility and consumer happiness in courier services is complex, especially with the influence of empathy. Research demonstrates that although tangibility is an important aspect of service quality, empathy is the paramount feature affecting customer happiness (Tang et al., 2022). A study employing the SERVQUAL model revealed that empathy exhibited the strongest link with customer satisfaction among diverse service quality criteria (Kodithuwakku and Weerasekera, 2023). The influence of tangibility on satisfaction is moderated by the perceived significance of empathy, indicating that when customers emphasize tangible service elements, their satisfaction markedly increases with the perception of elevated empathy from couriers (Pigao, 2023). This encounter underscores the imperative for courier services to harmonize concrete service components with compassionate client engagement to enhance satisfaction (Ekowati, 2023).

The remaining data, when categorized according to the evaluation of SERVQUAL dimensions of air express cargo operators and customer satisfaction levels based on their views, reveals no significant difference. Overall, the findings emphasize that customer satisfaction in courier services relies not only on delivering reliable and tangible services but also on fostering trust and emotional connection through assurance and empathy. By prioritizing these dimensions, courier operators can significantly enhance customer experiences, satisfaction, and long-term loyalty.

Table 21

Frequency Distribution and Ranking of Challenges in the Logistics Activities Encountered by an Air Express Cargo Client in Terms of using the Air express Operator's Services.

Challenges	Frequency	Percentage	Ranking
The platform of the courier is outdated.	29	31.868	1
Their system always encounters system maintenance.	22	24.175	2
Others	19	20.879	3
There is no 24/7 customer service support on their online platform.	9	9.890	4
Received the items with dent and packages are damaged.	6	6.593	5

The team showed carelessness in the task assigned to them.	2	2.198	6
Poor condition of packaging by the courier.	1	1.098	7
There is no online monitoring of shipment on their website.	1	1.098	7
The team lacks skills and urgency	1	1.098	7
Shipment overbooking.	1	1.098	7
TOTAL	91	100%	

Table 21 showed that most of the respondents encountered challenges is the platform of the courier is outdated with a percentage of 31.868 as rank 1. Followed by their system always encounters system maintenance with a percentage of 24.175 in rank 2, other challenges with a percentage of 20.879 in rank 3, there is no 24/7 customer service support on their online platform with a percentage of 9.890 at rank 4, received the items with dent and packages are damaged with a percentage of 6.593 at rank 5, the team showed carelessness in the task assigned to them with a percentage of 2.198 in rank 6 and the least is with a percentage of 1.098 at rank 7 comprising of: Poor condition of packaging by the courier, there is no online monitoring of shipment on their website, the team lacks skills and urgency and Shipment overbooking respectively.

Conventional courier systems face difficulties in scalability, efficiency, and user experience, prompting the creation of contemporary programs such as the Enhanced Courier Service System to tackle these issues (Sathish et al., 2024). The document emphasized that antiquated courier platforms encounter difficulties including insufficient digital integration, inefficiencies in cross-border logistics, and the necessity for modernization of international legal frameworks. The research highlights obsolete platforms as a major obstacle, affecting package safety and delivery efficiency in last-mile logistics, hence requiring contemporary solutions customized to varied consumer demands (Syuhailah et al., 2024). Challenges in system maintenance for courier services are guaranteeing uninterrupted connection among components, efficiently managing data flow, and adjusting to changing customer requirements while preserving performance and security (Sathish et al., 2024). Challenges in system maintenance for courier services encompass the management of booking information, tracking courier history, and assuring the accuracy of personnel and branch records, which become intricate when processed manually (Eka et al., 2022).

The absence of round-the-clock customer care support in e-commerce platforms, especially courier services, results in delayed replies and unresolved issues, adversely affecting consumer satisfaction and loyalty (Kanaan et al., 2023). The report identified insufficient customer service availability, particularly the absence of 24/7 support, as a critical concern affecting parcel safety and overall satisfaction in last-mile delivery. (Syuhailah et al. (2024).

Damage to packages, especially dents, is a considerable challenge in last-mile delivery, affecting overall cargo safety and consumer happiness in the postal and courier sectors (Syuhailah et al., 2024). Prompt and precise recognition of parcel damage, including dents, is essential for mitigating financial losses and improving customer satisfaction in logistics and shipping (Chaudhary & Singh, 2024).

According Syuhailah et al. (2024) courier services face challenges such as diverse consumer demographics, security issues, and the necessity for customized techniques to improve parcel safety and delivery dependability in various situations. Additionally, challenges in courier services encompass elevated operational expenses, customer satisfaction requirements, punctual delivery, return management, and the integration of flexible delivery alternatives such as package lockers to improve efficiency (Yu et al., 2022). The courier sector encounters various obstacles that affect both efficiency and safety, especially in last-mile deliveries. A major challenge is the intricacy of forecasting Estimated Time of Pick-up Arrival (ETPA), exacerbated by the multi-destination aspect of deliveries and the necessity for real-time updates on couriers' routes, affected by diverse spatial-temporal variables (Wen et al., 2023).

Moreover, guaranteeing item safety during last-mile delivery is essential, as demographic differences influence security protocols and client anticipations (Hussin et al., 2024). Couriers face operational challenges, such as unjust revenue assessments and insufficient assistance from food platforms, resulting in work-life imbalances and health hazards (Schnicke, 2023; Zong et al., 2024). Moreover, the proliferation of gig labor has intensified safety issues, as elevated accident rates have been seen among freelance riders (Schnicke, 2023). Confronting these problems is crucial for enhancing service quality and the welfare of couriers.

Addressing these multifaceted challenges is imperative not only for improving the quality of courier services but also for safeguarding the well-being of couriers. Proactive measures, such as leveraging advanced technologies for route optimization, enhancing workplace policies to ensure fair compensation and support, and implementing comprehensive safety training programs, are essential steps toward building a more resilient and sustainable courier industry. Additionally, fostering a collaborative approach among stakeholders—courier companies, platform providers, policymakers, and customers—can create a more balanced ecosystem that prioritizes efficiency, safety, and the overall welfare of couriers

Figure 1. Proposed logistics activity model for AECO (Packaging, Transportation and Order Fulfillment)

Based on the above results the researcher drew up a model that will be a basis for a logistics activity model with the following variables that primarily significant in AECO are reliability, assurance, empathy and tangibility. On the other hand, responsiveness has shown importance but compared to other variables it does not highlight its relevance.

The shipper is responsible for packing materials, which are provided by AECO as supplies, and ensuring that all goods comply with legal regulations. They also established a parcel drop box for efficient collection of shipments. AECO abroad serves as a centralized hub with the shipper's address, where they establish a cut-off time for scheduling airline reservations. Furthermore, they will make sure that packing materials are sufficient for the volume needs by the shipper. Additionally, they send pre-advice notices to the local AECO to ensure smooth coordination.

In another side, AECO local and AECO abroad should maintain the synchronization of transportation flow from origin to destination. Establishing a modern logistics tool can enhance the accuracy and timeliness of lead time. Moreover, local AECO operates as a centralized hub with the consignee's address, implementing a

monthly route optimization plan alongside a scheduled delivery plan to enhance efficiency. Finally, the consignee collaborates with a customer service provider of local AECO to manage the logistics of the delivery process, including the establishment of a parcel drop box for receiving shipments and a dashboard system for consignee to be established by local AECO for monitoring of order fulfillment and customer satisfaction of the consignee.

DISCUSSION

Based on the data gathered, the findings are listed below.

1. In terms of assessment of the quality services of air express cargo operators based on the SERVQUAL dimensions. The respondents showed reliability with the highest mean of 3.635 with interpretation of very important.
2. In terms of assessment of the quality of services in terms of reliability. Respondents emphasize the importance of promptly updating and communicating the tracking status of shipments to customers, as reflected by the highest mean score of 3.714 "Very Important".
3. In terms of assessment of the quality of services in terms of responsiveness. Respondents emphasize the accuracy and reliability in delivering the correct and accurate parcels, as reflected by the highest mean score of 3.670 "Very Important"
4. In terms of assessment of the quality of services in terms of assurance. Respondents emphasize the sense of security with the delivery man, as reflected by the highest mean score of 3.703 "Very Important"
5. In terms of assessment of the quality of services in terms of empathy. Respondents emphasize the availability of client assistance consistently, as reflected by the highest mean score of 3.648 "Very Important"
6. In terms of assessment of the quality of services in terms of tangibility. Respondents emphasize the user-friendly interface of the AECOs computer program, as reflected by the highest mean score of 3.593 "Very Important".
7. In terms of the level of customer satisfaction based on customer expectations. Respondents emphasize the importance of empathy, as reflected by the highest mean score of 3.262 "Very Satisfied"
8. In terms of the level of customer satisfaction in terms of customer expectation based on reliability. Respondents emphasize that they consistently deliver their service with precision, as reflected by the highest mean score of 3.198 "Satisfied"
9. In terms of the level of customer satisfaction in terms of customer expectation based on responsiveness. Respondents emphasize the accuracy and reliability in delivering the correct and accurate parcels, as reflected by the highest mean score of 3.220 " Satisfied"
10. In terms of the level of customer satisfaction in terms of customer expectation based on assurance. Respondents emphasize Sense of security with the delivery man., as reflected by the highest mean score of 3.286 "Very Satisfied"
11. In terms of the level of customer satisfaction in terms of customer expectation based on empathy. Respondents emphasize Service is cognizant of the clients' needs, as reflected by the highest mean score of 3.330 "Very Satisfied".

12. In terms of the level of customer satisfaction in terms of customer expectation based on tangibility. Respondents emphasize type of vehicles utilized, as reflected by the highest mean score of 3.198 "Satisfied"
13. In terms of the level of customer satisfaction based on customer perceptions. Respondents emphasize the importance of assurance, as reflected by the highest mean score of 3.389 "Very Satisfied".
14. In terms of the level of customer satisfaction in terms of customer perception based on reliability. Respondents emphasize the Consistently delivers its service with precision. as reflected by the highest mean score of 3.308 " Very Satisfied"
15. In terms of the level of customer satisfaction in terms of customer perception based on responsiveness. Respondents emphasize accuracy and reliability in delivering the correct and accurate parcels. as reflected by the highest mean score of 3.308 "Very Satisfied"
16. In terms of the level of customer satisfaction in terms of customer perception based on assurance. Respondents emphasize the Sense of security with the delivery man. as reflected by the highest mean score of 3.473 "Very Satisfied".
17. In terms of the level of customer satisfaction in terms of customer perception based on empathy. Respondents emphasize the Effective communication with the deliveryman and customer support crucial in resolving delivery. as reflected by the highest mean score of 3.396 " Very Satisfied"
18. In terms of the level of customer satisfaction in terms of customer perception based on tangibility. Respondents emphasize the Type of vehicles utilized. as reflected by the highest mean score of 3.363 " Very Satisfied".
19. With regards between the assessment of respondents on the empathy of air express cargo operators and the customer's level of satisfaction of reliability in terms of their expectations ($r=0.966$; $p<.05$) it shows that there is a positive, very high and significant relationship .The greater the importance of empathy, the higher the level of satisfaction with reliability, as perceived by customers based on their expectations.
20. With regards between the assessment of respondents on the assurance of air express cargo operators and the customer's level satisfaction of assurance in terms of their customer perception ($r=0.913$; $p<0.30$) shows that there is a positive, very high and significant relationship. Including assessment of respondents on the tangibility of air express cargo operators and the customers level of satisfaction of empathy in terms of their customer perception ($r=0.954$; $p<0.12$)
21. Majority of the surveyed respondents 'shows that most of the respondents encountered challenges is the platform of the courier is outdated with a percentage of 31.868.

Conclusions

1. Based on the assessment of SERVQUAL dimensions concludes mainly, that all variables are " Very important " as a SERVQUAL conclusion conveys the overall quality services of air express cargo operators. It was found that reliability had a comparatively higher score than the others among the five dimensions suggested by Qi et al. (2022).

Reliability is very important for the quality of courier service, since timeliness and accurate delivery contribute significantly toward customer satisfaction and customer loyalty for better competitive advantage in the industry.

This analysis of the five SERVQUAL dimensions indicated that the five areas are defined as "Very Important" in terms of overseeing the service quality of AECO. Of them, reliability is found to be the most significant dimension contributing to customer satisfaction and loyalty. Reliability, pertinent in its meaning to timely and accurate delivery, directly influences the prospect of customers placing trust in the courier service and affects the competitive advantage of the same for the service provider. The results show a predominant necessity for AECO to focus on reliability in its operations so as to maintain the overall quality of service, engender customer loyalty, and strengthen market position.

2. As to the conclusion about customer satisfaction based on customer expectations, the results show "Satisfied". However, the empathy dimension notably exhibited a better view of "Very Satisfied" based on the results. According to Tang et al. (2022), empathy was recognized practically as the critical variable between satisfaction and assurance. Notably, the tangibility dimension exhibits the lowest response; nevertheless, in terms of overall customer satisfaction based on customer perception, it reflected, "Very Satisfied". Among the dimensions, assurance was found with the highest level of satisfaction. In the assurance dimension, respondents expressed a feeling of security with the delivery personnel. According to Robin and Eyyanto (2023), respondents place a high value on feeling secure with the PT Lion Parcel delivery personnel, which carries a lot of weight for customer satisfaction. Moreover, as noted by Syuhailah et al. (2024), the respondents felt reasonably secure about working with delivery professionals, pointing to the significance of assurance in safeguarding packages during last-mile delivery. While the lowest among the variables is tangibility. In conclusion, though the tangibility dimension recorded the lowest mean score while judging service quality and customer satisfaction, it by no means means disregarding its worth. Tangible aspects in service-delivery ambiance, including the surrounding facility appearance, equipment, and professionalism in presentation, extended an essential foundation regarding the customer's perspective as well as the experience. This, therefore, necessitates a constant focus on improving the understanding of tangibility within the courier industry, and further investigation into tangibility is suggested for future researchers in order to provide deeper insights into further enhancing service quality and hence customer satisfaction as the industry continues its development into the foreseeable future.

3. The study showed that dimensions of service quality and customer satisfaction in the expression of the air express cargo operators have strong significant relations with each other. Specifically, the results show empathy had increasing levels of correlation with reliability satisfaction as in customer expectations. Widagdo et al. (2023) affirmed that customer satisfaction builds an important milestone in being influenced by empathy and reliability, hence establishing their significance toward maximization of overall service quality satisfaction. Found that reliability and empathy are both factors affecting customer satisfaction the most. The findings of this research revealed that in cases where reliability meets the customers' expectations, overall satisfaction with courier service is enhanced,

while on the other hand, empathy greatly influences customer satisfaction. Assurance is also positively associated with higher customer satisfaction regarding perception of assurance-contexts. Whereas assurance affects the customer's view of service quality in the courier sector positively, those giving assurance emphasis tend to exhibit higher levels of satisfaction. According to Bae and Janghyun (2024), tangibility is important too, as the greater importance placed on its effectiveness makes a significant contribution to customer satisfaction with empathy. While tangibility constituted one of the basic components of service quality, it also represented the most significant factor determining customer satisfaction, suggesting that it rather reflects the complex relationship than correlates straightforwardly (Qi et al. 2022). These results point out how various dimensions of service quality can interact with one another and how they affect satisfaction from a customer's standpoint. By focusing on empathy, assurance, and tangibility, air express cargo carriers can boost customers' views and in turn, meet or exceed expectations, which ultimately leads to loyalty and trust.

4. Different logistics issues have a negative effect on service efficiency, hence affecting customer satisfaction. The result showed that respondents ranked old-fashioned courier platforms as a real obstacle, for 31.868% quoted it as a major concern. This highlighted the urgent need to upgrade the IT infrastructure and software's used mistreated by air express cargo operators (AECO). For the platform to be upgraded will work towards better satisfaction from the customers, improved ease of running things, and reduced customer complaints, putting AECO in a position to fulfill the shifting needs of customers and gain competitive edges in the market.

5.As mentioned in the proposed model, the Air Express Cargo Operators (AECO) operational framework sets out to show very important functions that have to be performed by shippers, AECO abroad, AECO local, and consignees in facilitating the seamless flow of cargo from the point of origin to a destination. The shipper is responsible for properly packing the goods using materials supplied by AECO, as well as for other legal requirements. With a parcel drop box, shipment collection becomes much more convenient, and AECO abroad becomes a central hub for airline reservations and the provision of adequate packing materials. By sending pre-advice notices about this to local AECO, they improve cooperation and efficiency in an operation.

Locally, AECO has played a vital role in synchronizing transportation flow, armed with contemporary logistics tools that can boost the accuracy and timeliness of lead times. Local AECO is a central hub that connects to the consignee address, utilizing monthly optimized routes and a scheduling delivery system to enhance efficiencies. Collaboration with the consignee is also imperative to facilitate real-time tracking of orders by a dashboard system, creating transparency and an improved customer experience. The use of parcel drop boxes facilitates the efficient reception of shipments by consignees.

In essence, effective coordination and synchronization between shippers, AECO abroad, AECO local, and consignees are indispensable for ensuring operational efficiency, timely delivery, and customer satisfaction. Using modern logistics tools to

improve transparency and fill gaps in supply chain processes could contribute significantly in this respect to the enhancement of AECO service quality and customer experience.

Recommendations

Based on the overall findings from the collected data in this study, the following recommendations are given:

1. To improve the overall quality of air express cargo operators services , numerous critical areas can be refined: 1) Prioritizing dedicated customer service guarantees clients receive prompt assistance and problem resolution, hence cultivating trust; 2) Enhancing courier efficiency accelerates deliveries, guaranteeing that products arrive promptly and dependably. Moreover, delivery people must continually exhibit respect and professionalism to foster pleasant encounters with recipients. Customized attention, including the adjustment of delivery preferences, improves the client experience. 3) Ultimately, upholding professional clothes for couriers conveys a credible and refined image, enhancing the company's professionalism and dependability. Collectively, these enhancements augment service quality and client pleasure.

2. To fulfill and surpass consumer expectations, AECO can improve its air express courier services in several ways: 1) Enhancing dedicated customer service is essential by ensuring team members are perpetually prepared to address client concerns, providing prompt and efficient resolutions; 2) Delivery professionals must consistently demonstrate respect and professionalism to foster a positive and professional contact with customers; 3) Furthermore, ensuring the continuous availability of customer assistance means support is accessible at all times; 4) Ultimately, mandating couriers to don professional clothes reinforces a robust brand image and cultivates client trust. These enhancements can substantially elevate consumer happiness and loyalty.

To boost client perception of AECO's air express courier services, numerous improvements are suggested. Firstly, ensuring that shipment tracking is promptly updated and accurately disclosed to clients would enhance transparency and trust. Ensuring consistent availability for customer service is essential, guaranteeing that support is accessible when required. Delivery professionals must consistently exhibit respect and courtesy, thereby enhancing the client experience. Moreover, customer care should be vigilant and compassionate, resolving issues with sensitivity and professionalism. Enhancing the user-friendliness of AECO's software will facilitate interactions, rendering the service more convenient and efficient for users. These enhancements will enhance client happiness and loyalty.

3. Businesses should put empathy at the forefront of their customer service strategy in order to increase customer satisfaction with perceived reliability. consumers are more likely to believe that their expectations are fulfilled and to have greater faith in the reliability of the business when staff members who interact with consumers actually comprehend and address their requirements, worries, and feelings. This can be accomplished through teaching staff members to identify emotional signs, promoting

active listening, and fostering tailored interactions that demonstrate consideration for each person's needs. Furthermore, clients are reassured and trust is increased by sympathetic, open communication, especially during delays or service interruptions. Businesses can close the gap between customers' expectations and their real service experience and increase reliability satisfaction by regularly demonstrating empathy in customer interactions.

Air Express Cargo Operators should place a strong priority on providing high levels of assurance in order to increase customer satisfaction with air express cargo services. According to research, there is a direct correlation between customers' pleasure with assurance and how they evaluate its attributes, such as professionalism, dependability, and knowledge. Customers are more satisfied when they place a higher value on assurance since it meets their expectations for reliable service. Air cargo operators should concentrate on continuously exhibiting dependability and proficiency, possibly through staff development, open communication, and quality control procedures. They can increase overall happiness, strengthen customer trust, and enhance views of service assurance by doing this.

Furthermore, Air express cargo operators should concentrate on improving tangible components of their service to increase customer satisfaction because this has a significant impact on empathy perceptions. As mentioned in previous studies, clients are more satisfied with the service provider's empathy when they place a higher value on tangibles such the facilities' look, the caliber of the equipment, and the staff's professional demeanor. The idea that the operator values the needs of the consumer is reinforced by tangible components that give the appearance of care and attentiveness. AECO can demonstrate a strong sense of empathy by investing in clean, aesthetically pleasing facilities, up-to-date machinery, and professional clothing for employees. This will increase customer satisfaction and build more supportive and trustworthy relationships with clients.

4. To address the problem of an outdated courier platform, various strategic enhancements are required. Initially, allocate resources to improve the platform's infrastructure to augment speed, reliability, and security. Utilize contemporary technologies, including cloud-based solutions, to enhance scalability and performance. The platform must be designed for mobile devices, facilitating effortless access to services for users on-the-go.

Subsequently, enhance the user interface (UI) and user experience (UX) to make the ERP system more intuitive and user-friendly, ensuring users can navigate and utilize its features effortlessly. Implementing an ERP system in the organization not only streamlines processes but also boosts the efficiency and effectiveness of organizational resources, enabling better decision-making, improved productivity, and optimized resource allocation.

This entails streamlining navigation, facilitating real-time shipment tracking, automation tools to optimize procedures such order management, notifications, and

tracking changes. Consistent upgrades and maintenance are crucial to maintain the platform's functionality and relevance. Providing tutorials or customer training on the new system will facilitate user acceptance, mitigate resistance, and enhance overall satisfaction.

5. In order to be a real betterment in efficiency and customer satisfaction, AECO should invest in other modern-logistics methods, including automated tracking systems and real-time dashboards, to measure lead time better in terms of accuracy and transparency. Operations will ultimately be streamlined further by strengthening coordination among shippers, AECO abroad, and local AECO through mechanized and digitalized means of communication. As parcels can be easily deposited and conveniently picked up from locations secondly located, this could mean improved convenience and will also ensure a reduction in transit times. The local AECO ought to use new tools for realizing optimized delivery routes and enabling scheduled delivery plans to augment efficiency. A dashboard through which the customers can view real shipment tracking along with ongoing customer support could improve the overall customer experience. Full and regular assessments of supply chain processes and gathering feedback from stakeholders are critical to continuous proper improvement and maintenance of service excellence.

6. Future researchers are encouraged to explore the integration of advanced technologies such as AI, IoT, and blockchain into air express cargo services, as these innovations could enhance service quality dimensions like reliability and responsiveness while boosting customer satisfaction. Comparative studies across industries can identify best practices and innovative strategies to improve service delivery. Additionally, examining cultural and regional differences will provide valuable insights into tailoring services to meet the unique needs of diverse customer bases. Longitudinal studies are also recommended to assess how customer satisfaction and perceptions of service quality evolve over time, particularly following the implementation of service improvements such as platform upgrades or enhanced staff training.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

There was no conflict of interest to declare in this study. Participants' benefits were not affected by answering the survey.

The records from this study was kept confidential as possible. The respondents can choose to write or not write their personal identity in the survey questionnaire. Once they receive the answered survey, the researcher created a code/number to represent their identity. Their individual identities will not be disclosed in any reports or publications resulting from the study. All questionnaires, transcripts, summaries, notes, documents will be stored separately. Research information were always kept in locked files in google drive. All the data was stored for around two years. After two years, the data will be deleted carefully and permanently from the stored place. The UERC will be given access to all the data for evaluation purposes including personal identity related information. The statistician also gave access to the data for computation purposes. The research adviser

was given access to the data for confirmation purposes. The completed research paper will be stored in the database of Adamson University, students/faculty members in Adamson might have the access to check the paper for reference purposes.

The informed consent form will be shown to the targeted respondents during the recruitment process. Once they have read the informed consent form and are willing to participate in the survey, the survey link will be sent to them accordingly.

There are no vulnerabilities involved in the study.

In this study, the respondent's recruitment proceeded following the steps: 1) Sending a message/mail/letter to the targeted respondents along with informed consent form. 2) If targeted respondents are willing to answer the survey, the survey link will be sent to the respondents Assent. The respondents are targeted as the adults who have worked/are working in importers, no underage participants will be involved in the study.

The study will specifically focused on adults who have experience or employed. No individuals below the legal age of adulthood will be included in the research.

It is supposed that there is no risk involved in participating in this questionnaire. However, there is a possibility the participants may feel uncomfortable or inconvenient during the process of answering the questionnaire. Any questions participants are not willing to answer, they had the option to skip them and move on to the next question.

There were no incentives/benefits provided to the participants for answering the survey. However, their contribution in answering the survey may help the researcher to obtain information on improving the performance of call center companies.

There was no financial or material gifts to be provided from answering the survey, the participation was totally voluntary.

The study aimed to provide some suggestions and ideas on how to improve employee performance in importer companies, so there will be no negative impact on the community. The personal benefits of the participants were not impacted as well.

The study is done by the researcher only with the guidance/suggestions of the adviser. There are no collaborations with other groups.

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